

A Study on Prescribing Pattern of Antibiotics in Lower Respiratory Tract Infection at A Tertiary Care Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Respiratory tract infections are the common health problem in India. Antibiotics are predominantly used in the management of Lower Respiratory Tract Infection. This Prospective observational study was conducted for a period of 6 months in a tertiary care hospital in South India. A total of 150 patients with age above 18 years of either gender, diagnosed with lower respiratory tract infection on antibiotics were included in the study. The patient's demographic details such as age, gender, social history, previous allergies, past medical and medication history, diagnosis. Patient's laboratory investigation, Chest radiographs and culture sensitivity test were noted. Antibiotic therapy including the route of administration, dose, dosage, frequency, and duration were evaluated. The data was analysed using statistical software SPSS. Of the total 150 patients, male were 59% and female 41%. Majority of the patients were with age > 65 years (50.7%). The common co-morbidities observed was HTN and DM. Most predominant LRTI was AECOPD (27.3%) and Pneumonia (27.3%). Out of 352 antibiotics, most commonly prescribed antibiotic was penicillin (23.7%). About 63% of the patients were with monotherapy and 53% patients were on dual therapy. It is concluded that using antibiotics wisely will reduce multidrug resistance, enhances patient care and following treatment guidelines improves the quality of treatment.

Keywords: LRTI, Antibiotics, prescribing pattern, resistance, culture sensitivity

INTRODUCTION

One of the most common health issues is lower respiratory tract infections (LRTIs). The LRTIs include bronchitis, bronchiectasis, bronchiolitis, emphysema, lung abscess, pleural effusion acute exacerbation of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and pneumonia⁽¹⁾⁽²⁾. Lower respiratory tract infections (LRTI) are common human diseases, whose morbidity and mortality fluctuate based on the virulence of the underlying etiological agent.⁽³⁾ Aetiology of LRTI's depend on various demographic characteristics that include the place of study (rural/urban), age (young/middle/old), other predisposing factors including hospitalization.⁽⁴⁾ The major respiratory pathogens are Gram negative bacilli (GNB) like *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (*K.pneumoniae*), *Escherichia coli* (*Esch.coli*),

Pseudomonas aeruginosa (*P.aeruginosa*), *Acinetobacter* species, other Non-Fermentative Gram-Negative Bacilli (NFGNB) and gram positive organisms like *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (*Str.pneumoniae*), *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S.aureus*).⁽²⁾ Appropriate information about organisms isolated and their sensitivity pattern is essential for choosing suitable antibiotics among multiple antibiotics available.⁽¹³⁾

Antibiotics are the first line treatment in lower respiratory tract infections. However, antibiotic is not indicated in viral infections. It is essential to choose the right antibiotic depending on the organism and to make sure that the therapy responds to the evolving characteristics of these infections and the increase resistance to conventional therapies.⁽⁵⁾ Antimicrobial resistance in bacterial pathogens is a worldwide

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

challenge associated with high morbidity and mortality. Multidrug resistant patterns in Gram-positive and -negative bacteria has emerged as difficult task in treating or even resulted in infections untreatable with conventional therapies.⁽⁶⁾ Appropriate use of antibiotics has contributed to the control of infectious diseases and the reduction of mortality. However, there are serious problems concerning the inadequate use of antibiotics. Misuse of antibiotics, particularly broad spectrum antibiotics, in tertiary care hospitals is a major contributing factor to reduced drug efficacy, increased prevalence of resistant pathogens in the community, and the appearance of new co-infections. The prescribing pattern deals with monitoring, evaluating and suggesting modifications in the prescribing pattern, in order to provide patient care with safe, effective and cost effective.⁽⁷⁾ This study deals with prescribing patterns of antibiotics in lower respiratory tract infection, determining the prevalence of microbial aetiology of LRTIs and their susceptibility profile.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This prospective observational study was carried out in the Department of General Medicine, Vijaya groups of hospital Vadapalani, Chennai for a period of six months. All in-patient of either sex, patients diagnosed with lower respiratory tract infection on antibiotics and patients age above 18years were included for the study. Out patients, pregnant and

lactating women, patients with Tuberculosis, H1N1 and COVID 19 patients were excluded. With approval from the institutional ethics committee, Vijaya Hospital (IEC/VBMHR/LTR/2022/029) and the patients meeting the inclusion criteria the following methods were followed. The patient's demographics details such as age, sex, co-morbidities, diagnosis, laboratory investigation, Chest radiographs and culture sensitivity test were recorded. For the detailed analysis of the patients, the bacteriological profile and culture sensitivity test, Use of antibiotic for therapeutic or prophylactic purpose were recorded.

Antibiotic therapy including the route of administration, dose, dosage, frequency and duration, number and class of antibiotics used, switch from parenteral to oral antibiotic and switch off or addition of different groups of antibiotics were recorded. The patients were followed till discharge. Statistical analysis was performed by the statistical software SPSS version 23. The results are expressed as frequency and percentages.

RESULT:

About 150 patients, were included in the study. The demographic details are represented in (table 1). Among the study population, majority of the patients were in non-critical care unit (94%) and 6% patients were in critical care unit.

Table 1. Demographic profile of study population

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE	PARAMETER	NUMBER OF PATIENTS (%)
AGE	18 – 45	18 (12)
	46 – 65	56 (37)
	>65	76 (51)
Gender	Male	89(59)
	Female	61(41)
COMORBIDITIES	Hypertension	94 (28)
	Diabetes mellitus	81 (24)
	Coronary artery disease	37 (11)
	COPD	36 (11)
	Asthma	15 (5)
	Chronic kidney disease	7 (2)
	Others	48 (14)
	No co-morbidity	18 (5)

Various lab investigations were carried out to confirm and categorise the diagnosis for lower respiratory tract infection. Common diagnostic tests were Chest X-ray + Sputum test in 31.3% of the patients, followed by Chest X-ray + HR CT – Sputum test in

18.7% of patients, HRCT + Sputum 10.7%, Chest X-ray in 11.3%, Sputum test in 8.7%, Other diagnostic test (lab parameter) in 7.3% patients, HR CT in 6.7%, Chest X-ray – HR CT 5.3% patients. The diagnosis of these patients is depicted in Fig 1

Figure 2: Distribution of the study population based on diagnosis

Out of 150 study population, culture test was performed in 106 (70.6%) patients. The reports indicate, 12.7% with Gram negative organism, 2.7% with Gram positive organism and no growth of microorganism observed in (55.3%) patients. The predominant organisms identified in the culture was *Klebsiella pneumonia* in 61% of the patients, followed by 17% with *Streptococcus pneumonia*, 17% with *E.coli* and 5% with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. In antibiotic susceptibility pattern, the resistance pattern of antibiotics indicate highest resistance with ampicillin (n=14) followed by amoxicillin clavulanic acid (n=10), ciprofloxacin (n=10), levofloxacin (n=7), cefazolin (n=4), tigecycline (n=3), cefexime (n=1) and cefuroxime (n=1) and the sensitivity pattern, indicate highest sensitivity towards to cefoperazone sulbactam (n=9), piperacillin tazobactam (n=6), levofloxacin (n=3), cefepime tazobactam (n=8), meropenam (n=6), Polymycin B (n=5) followed by amoxicillin clavulanic acid (n=5), doxycycline (n=5), azithromycin (n=4).

Out of antibiotics prescribed, 823.7% patients were with penicillin, 18.9% were with fluoroquinolone,

13.3% were with cephalosporin, 10.9% were with tetracycline, 10.1% were with carbapenem, 8.5% were with macrolide, 4.5% were with lincomycin, 1.6% were with oxazolidinone, 1.1% were with polypeptide, 0.5% were with aminoglycoside and 20.5% were with glycopeptide.

Among the antibiotics prescribed, majority of (20.4%) prescription was with inj. Piperacillin + tazobactam, followed by 11% with inj. levofloxacin, 10.7% with Inj. Meropenam, 9% with Inj. Cefoperazone + Sulbactam, 7.1% with T. Azithromycin, 5.6% with T. levofloxacin, 16 (4.5%) were T. Doxycycline, 15 (4.2%) were Inj. Clindamycin, 14 (4%) were inj. doxycycline, 12 (3.4%) were inj. amoxicillin + clavulanic acid, 10 (3%) were c. doxycycline, 6 (1.7%) were inj. ciprofloxacin, and other 49 (14%) antibiotics were t. moxifloxacin, inj. polymycin, t. ciprofloxacin, c. cefuroxime, t. ciprofloxacin, inj. amikacin, inj. azithromycin. (Figure 4) Spectrum of antibiotics of study population, 345 (98.1%) were broad spectrum antibiotics and 7 (1.9%) were narrow spectrum antibiotics. Out of 352 antibiotics, majority of 244 (69.3%) antibiotics were administered in

parenteral route and 108 (30.7%) were oral route. Out of 352 antibiotics, 244 (69.3%) were injections, 97 (27.6%) were tablets and 11 (3.1%) were capsules.

Figure 3: Antibiotics prescribed among the study population

Out of 352 antibiotics, 154 (43.8%) were prescribed for less than 5 days, 118 (33.6%) were prescribed for 5 days, 78 (22.1%) were prescribed for more than 5 days and 2 (0.5%) drugs were hold. The majority of

80 (53%) patients were treated with dual therapy, followed by 31 (21%) patients were treated with mono therapy, 26 (17%) patients were treated with triple therapy and 13 (9%) patients were treated with multiple therapy. (Figure 4)

Figure 4: Drug pattern

DISCUSSION

The current study provides data on prescribing patterns of antibiotics for LRTI among in-patient. Out of 150 patients diagnosed with LRTI, the most commonly observed patients belonged to >65 years age group (51%) which was similar to the study conducted by Rajaseger Nirmal Kumar et al.⁽⁵⁾ where

in The incidence of clinically-defined LRTI was 248 per 1000 person-years among older adults.

In our study 59% were male and 41% were female. Out of 150 patients, almost all the patients had comorbidities among which the most predominant one was hypertension 28% (n=94) were similar to study conducted by Shyama K et al.⁽⁴⁾

In the present study 150 patients were diagnosed with LRTI's which were further categorized and among these AECOPD 27.3%, pneumonia 27.3%, and LRTI (unspecified) 17.3% were predominant, these was similar to study carried out by Divya kancherla et al., 2015, in which it was observed that LRTI (unspecific) accounted for 41.79% and pneumonia was in 23.88%.⁽²⁾ The most common diagnostic tests performed to confirm LRTI in our study was Chest X-ray with Sputum test 31.3% (47). Culture sensitivity analysis in LRTI's is important to provide better patient outcome by prescribing accurate antibiotic therapy and decreases the emerging drug resistance. Out of 106 culture samples, 55.3% (n=83) patients were reported with no growth of microorganism, 12.7% (n=19) patients were reported with Gram negative organism and 2.7% (n=4) were reported with Gram positive organism which is similar to study by Regha IR et al., 2018 where they reported more Gram -negative organism 84.7% (n=288). In present study the most common organism identified in culture among gram negative organism was Klebsiella pneumonia 61% (n=14) and among gram positive organism was Streptococcus pneumoniae 17% (n=4) which is similar to study by Regha IR et al., 2018.⁽⁶⁾ Antibiotic susceptibility test of the study represents that 61% Gram negative organism (Klebsiella pneumonia) were high resistance to Ampicillin and high sensitivity to Cefoperazone sulbactam, Piperacillin tazobactam, levofloxacin and Polymycin B which related to the study by Rakshya Nepal et al.⁽⁷⁾

Of the total antibiotics prescribed (n=352), most common class of antibiotic prescribed were penicillin 23.7% (n=89) and fluoroquinolone 18% (n=71). The most predominant antibiotic used were piperacillin + tazobactam 20.4% (n=72), levofloxacin 11% (n=39) as they have equivalent or better efficacy than standard comparative regimen in LRTI. This was contrast to the study conducted by Divya Kancherla et al., 2015 found the following antibiotic class being commonly prescribed, penicillins 46.5%, fluoroquinolones 34.4%, cephalosporin 89.6% and macrolides 62.6%.⁽²⁾ Spectrum of antibiotics of study population, 345 (98.1%) were broad spectrum antibiotics and 7 (1.9%) were narrow spectrum antibiotics. In our study among 150 patients, two patients were escalated with the dose of meropenam from 1g to 1.5g to improve the efficacy of the drug for

better patient treatment. The route of administration for most of the patients was injections 69.3% (n=244) followed by tablets and a very few on capsules. Most of the study population in our study were treated with dual drug therapy 53% (n=80) than mono therapy 21% (n=31) and triple therapy 17% (n=26). Commonly prescribed fixed dose combination of antibiotic was piperacillin + tazobactam for treatment of LRTI's, which is similar to the study conducted by Rajaseger Nirmal Kumar et al., 2019⁽⁵⁾ and Mirza A. Beg et al., 2017.⁽⁸⁾ The advantage of prescribing fixed dose combinations was increased synergy, reduced side effects and costs.

CONCLUSION

In our study, the most commonly diagnosed disease among LRTI's was acute exacerbation of COPD and pneumonia. All the antibiotics prescribed were rational. Most of the drugs prescribed were given empirically with broad spectrum antibiotics such as Piperacillin+tazobactam, levofloxacin and Meropenam. Antimicrobial stewardship can be followed to avoid antibiotic over use and antimicrobial resistance. It can be concluded that the cautious and judicious use of antibiotic will decrease the multidrug resistance and thereby improves better patient management. Improvement in the quality of treatment can be done by adherence to standard treatment guidelines.

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HOW TO CITE: Puviyarasi K.*, Rajeshkumar K., Sanjhana C., Divya Sankar S., Sai krishna P., A Study on Prescribing Pattern of Antibiotics in Lower Respiratory Tract Infection at A Tertiary Care Hospital, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, 1 (11), 1089-1094. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17659589>

